

Unlocking Energy from Waste Heat through Electricity Market Interaction and Site-Integrated Thermal Storage

Phillip Duckett
p.g.a.duckett@sms.ed.ac.uk
University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Prof. Daniel Friedrich
d.friedrich@ed.ac.uk
University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Abstract

The provision of reliable and affordable low-carbon heat remains a significant challenge for the UK energy system, particularly in regions where dispersed demand, infrastructure constraints and commercial uncertainty limit investment in district heating networks (DHNs). Energy from Waste (EfW) facilities generate substantial volumes of recoverable thermal energy, yet much of this resource is routinely rejected to the environment. This paper presents a framework for integrating EfW-derived heat into district heating systems through the combined application of opportunity-cost based heat pricing and large-scale thermal energy storage. Using the East Lothian Heat Project as a case study, the research develops a commercial methodology which values heat according to the foregone revenue associated with reduced electricity generation, thereby establishing a transparent and economically grounded basis for heat pricing. The study further evaluates the role of large-scale thermal storage, including the novel use of a co-developed storage facility within an active limestone quarry, in improving system flexibility and reducing consumer heat costs. A techno-economic optimisation model is developed to examine the interaction between heat demand, storage operation and electricity market dynamics. The findings demonstrate that integrating thermal storage with opportunity-cost pricing can improve the commercial viability of EfW heat utilisation while enhancing security of supply and reducing the levelised cost of heat. The proposed framework offers a scalable and replicable model for local authorities seeking to develop affordable and resilient district heating infrastructure.

1 Introduction

Decarbonising heat remains one of the most challenging aspects of the United Kingdom's transition towards a net-zero energy system. While significant progress has been achieved in reducing the carbon

intensity of electricity generation, the deployment of low-carbon heating solutions has proceeded more slowly. District heating networks are increasingly recognised as a critical component of future heat decarbonisation strategies; however, their development is frequently constrained by high capital costs, uncertain demand profiles and challenges in securing reliable low-carbon heat sources. At the same time, substantial volumes of thermal energy are currently wasted within existing energy infrastructure. Energy from Waste (EfW) facilities, which play an increasingly important role in residual waste management, generate significant amounts of recoverable heat as a by-product of electricity production. In many cases, however, this heat is rejected to the environment through cooling systems despite representing a potentially valuable local energy resource. The underutilisation of EfW heat reflects a broader disconnect between waste management systems and local energy infrastructure.

Although the technical integration of EfW facilities with district heating networks through combined heat and power (CHP) operation is well established, deployment within the UK has lagged behind comparable European countries. The barriers are predominantly commercial rather than technical. For EfW operators, heat extraction reduces electricity output and therefore lowers revenues from electricity markets. Existing approaches to heat pricing, typically based on alternative fuel benchmarks or negotiated agreements, often fail to capture this relationship, resulting in uncertainty for both heat suppliers and consumers.

This paper addresses these challenges through the development of an integrated commercial and operational framework for EfW heat utilisation. Using the East Lothian Heat Project as a case study, the research investigates how opportunity-cost-based heat pricing and large-scale thermal energy storage can support the development of affordable, resilient and commercially viable district heating systems. Particular attention is given to the increasing interaction between heat and electricity markets and the role of storage in enabling operational flexibility.

The contribution of the work is twofold. First, it introduces a transparent methodology for valuing heat based on the opportunity cost of foregone electricity generation. Second, it demonstrates how large-scale thermal storage can improve both system economics and operational resilience by decoupling heat generation from heat demand. Together, these contributions provide a framework capable

* Both authors contributed equally to this research

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of supporting wider deployment of EfW-derived heat within district heating systems.

2 Background

The dramatic rise in recent history of global population and urbanisation has led to a significant increase in waste generation [9]. The traditional linear model of consumption, characterised by the extraction of raw materials, production, consumption and disposal, has contributed to large-scale environmental challenges. In response to the growing urgency for sustainable solutions, the adoption of circular economy principles in waste management has emerged as a critical paradigm shift [16]. Increasing environmental pressures, alongside the recognition of the finite nature of natural resources, have accelerated the transition towards more sustainable systems.

The circular economy offers an alternative to the conventional linear model by prioritising reduction, reuse, recycling and recovery of resources [10]. Fundamentally, it seeks to establish a closed-loop system which minimises waste generation while maximising resource efficiency through sustainable practices. Integrating circular economy principles into waste management is therefore essential for reducing environmental impacts associated with linear systems, while also creating new economic opportunities [8].

Beyond material recycling, the recovery of heat from waste streams represents a particularly valuable strategy within the circular economy, enabling the capture and reuse of thermal energy which would otherwise be lost. Technologies such as EfW incineration and industrial heat recovery systems allow excess heat to be redirected for district heating and industrial processes, thereby enhancing overall system efficiency [1]. Embedding heat recovery into waste management practices strengthens the circular economy's objective of optimising resource utilisation while reducing dependence on primary energy sources [7].

Importantly, the circular economy also delivers economic benefits. Unlike the traditional “take, make, dispose” model, which is both environmentally harmful and economically inefficient, circular approaches align economic development with environmental sustainability. Emphasising heat recovery further contributes to cost savings by improving energy efficiency and reducing operational expenditures across sectors.

Moreover, circular economy principles drive innovation by encouraging businesses to rethink conventional models. Organisations are motivated to design sustainable products, explore alternative materials, and implement closed-loop systems which incorporate thermal energy recovery [4]. This not only addresses environmental challenges but also creates new pathways for economic growth. Additionally, circular practices support the development of innovative business models such as product-as-a-service, further reinforcing the transition towards a sustainable and resource-efficient economic system [2].

EfW plants are an increasingly important component of the UK's waste management and energy infrastructure. By diverting residual waste from landfills and converting it into electricity, these facilities contribute both to emissions reduction and energy recovery.

Crucially, EfW plants also produce substantial volumes of thermal energy as a by-product of electricity generation. In many cases, however, this heat is not utilised and is instead rejected to the environment via cooling systems, representing a significant inefficiency within the broader energy system.

The integration of EfW facilities with district heating networks – commonly through combined heat and power (CHP) operation – offers a pathway to capture and utilise this otherwise wasted resource. Despite its technical maturity, deployment has been limited in the UK compared to other European countries. This is due in part to commercial and operational barriers. For EfW operators, extracting heat typically reduces electricity output, which directly impacts revenue in wholesale electricity markets. Without a clear and transparent mechanism for valuing heat, there is limited incentive to prioritise heat export over electricity generation.

Conventional approaches to heat pricing often rely on comparisons with alternative heating fuels, such as gas boilers, or are based on negotiated tariffs that may not fully reflect the underlying system economics. These methods can lead to misaligned incentives, prolonged negotiations, and uncertainty for both heat suppliers and consumers. As a result, potentially viable projects may fail to progress due to perceived commercial risk.

In parallel, electricity markets have become increasingly dynamic, with prices exhibiting greater volatility due to the growing penetration of intermittent renewable generation. This volatility introduces both challenges and opportunities. For EfW plants operating in CHP mode, there is a need to balance heat and electricity outputs in response to market signals. However, without flexibility in heat demand or storage, this balancing act is constrained, limiting the ability to optimise overall system value.

Phase Three of East Lothian Heat project [6] identifies a unique and timely opportunity to address these challenges through an integrated, multi-sector approach. At its core is the proposition to connect an EfW facility to a new district heating network, supported by large-scale thermal energy storage. This provides a valuable case study on which to center this framework, investigating the potential to transform a currently underutilised heat resource into a reliable, low-carbon heat supply for local communities.

A key innovation within this project is the development of a commercial framework that values heat based on the opportunity cost of foregone electricity generation. By explicitly modelling the thermodynamic relationship between heat extraction and electrical output, the project establishes a transparent and economically grounded basis for heat pricing. This approach provides a defensible lower bound for heat value, ensuring that EfW operators are adequately compensated while enabling local authorities to negotiate affordable tariffs for consumers.

Equally significant is the exploration of large-scale thermal energy storage as a mechanism for unlocking system flexibility. The proposed use of a nearby limestone quarry – where operators are willing to co-develop a purpose shaped storage void represents a novel approach to reducing capital costs associated with storage deployment. By integrating storage into ongoing extractive activities, the project

minimises the need for standalone excavation and civil engineering works, which are typically among the largest cost components.

Thermal storage enables the decoupling of heat generation from heat demand, allowing excess heat to be captured during periods of low electricity prices and dispatched when demand is high or when electricity prices incentivise reduced generation. This capability not only enhances security of supply for the district heating network but also allows the EfW plant to operate more flexibly within electricity markets, improving overall system efficiency.

Through detailed techno-economic modelling, the project evaluates how different storage configurations and operational strategies influence the levelised cost of heat (LCoH), system resilience, and peak demand management. The findings aim to provide actionable insights into the conditions under which integrated EfW and thermal storage systems deliver net economic and social benefits.

Ultimately, this phase of the East Lothian Heat Project demonstrates how coordinated planning across waste management, heat infrastructure, and extractive industries can unlock new pathways for scalable and commercially viable heat deployment. By aligning technical innovation with robust commercial structures, it offers a replicable model for other regions facing similar challenges in the transition to low-carbon heat systems.

3 Commercial Model

The commercial model is structured to quantify the economic implications of diverting energy from electricity generation to heat supply. The model integrates spatially derived heat demand and available storage capacity volume with temporally resolved market considerations to balance the opportunity cost of heat generation in lieu of electricity generation for the plant operator with minimal heat cost for the consumer. To approach this, we distinguish between the physical trade-offs in plant performance; the ‘generation cost’, and the associated financial impacts; the ‘commercial cost’, enabling a consistent valuation of heat within an electricity-dominated market framework.

Since this framework is built on national electricity pricing, some heating characteristics are lost. That is, since electricity is valued on a national scale it will fail to reflect where heat is less valuable to the local system either as a result of an abundance of lower-price stored heat or diminished heat consumption demand. To account for this, a heat demand profile is required at sufficient granularity to reflect the demand-driven value of heat in a given period. This is addressed in the following section before evaluating the opportunity cost of heat generation as the final component of deriving a ‘fair’ heat price.

3.1 Heat demand profile

Granularity of heat demand data is a key obstacle to meaningful heat valuation. High geospatial heat demand estimates are available in Scotland from the Scottish Government’s ‘Scotland Heat Map’ [14]. This tool aggregates a number of data sources available to the Scottish Government to estimate heat demand across Scotland in a 50m square grid allowing spatial analysis of heat demand. The

limitation of this data is that it is shared at an annual granularity which obscures the true demand profile at a meaningful resolution.

To address this, we require an hourly demand curve which can be used to spread the annual heat demand volume across the relevant time series, allowing a more indicative reflection of heat demand at a consumer level. To achieve this, we take the hourly heat demand profiles generated by Brockelbank et al. in their case study of Darley Dale in England [13]. This is sensible given the approximate similarities between Dunbar and the case study location. Brockelbank et al.’s study [13] is based around a lead-acid battery recycling plant and the nearby towns of Darley Dale, Matlock, Rowsley, Bakewell, Youlgrave and Cromford with a collective population of 21,700 [11], roughly twice the size of Dunbar.

While the total heat demand from the case study will likely overestimate in the case of Dunbar, the general shape should be appropriate to scale for an indicative heat demand curve. This is achieved by distributing the annual heat demand across the year using the normalised hourly profiles. This approach preserves the relative shape and variability of demand over time while ensuring that the annual demand remains consistent with locally derived estimates. The daily demand curve for each of the four seasons is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Daily Heat Demand Profile

Clearly the curves presented in Figure 1 capture simplistic seasonality, however more realistic consumption patterns aren’t reflected in this model. Notably some characteristics which aren’t captured are seasonality at smaller timescales, for example differing heat demand patterns in the week versus the weekend or across holiday periods. Sensitivity to this can be addressed in future work.

For now, using this heat demand profile paired with a heat storage capacity variable will allow an estimate of the value of heat more accurately. This is because it captures the trade-offs involved in generating heat and reflects how that value depends on when heat is actually needed. It is to this topic that we now turn our attention.

3.2 Generation cost

The generation cost reflects the physical relationship between heat production and electricity output. In CHP facilities, the extraction of useful heat reduces the amount of electricity that can be generated from a given input. This trade-off can be represented by a conversion factor, typically expressed as the marginal reduction in electrical output per unit of heat supplied. Naturally, this conversion factor will vary by technology, operating regime, age of equipment etc., but can be estimated for the purposes of this case study.

Conversion factors are fairly consistent across literature, with most sources pointing to electricity export only versus CHP performance

framed in terms of thermal efficiency rather than an explicit opportunity cost. See, for example, the Scottish Parliament's briefing note from 2022 which provides an overview of regulation and policy developments impacting EfW in Scotland [15]. In this, it is noted that new waste treatment plants in Scotland are required to achieve at least 20% energy recovery as a prerequisite to environmental licensing citing DEFRA's analysis that EfW sites in electricity export only conditions can achieve efficiencies of 20-27% [5] or in CHP mode efficiencies in excess of 60% [12]. It should be noted that these efficiency assumptions are 10-20 years out of date at the time of writing and so may not be reflective of modern technologies.

The thermal efficiencies are of limited use in evaluating a conversion factor, however in the case study of Viridor for Phase Three of the East Lothian Heat project, explicit generation figures are given in the Permit to Operate granted by the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) [13]. Specifically, in the Variation of Permit effective from July 2023, the technical specification indicates the plant is capable of exporting "either 33.72MW electrical without heat export, or 30.25MW electrical and up to 17.85MW of heat as low pressure steam or hot water" [13].

An important factor to consider here are losses. There are of course a number of losses which will apply as the heat and electricity is exported from the plant. The Variation of Permit [13] gives that the site's "generator [is] capable of generating a total of 36MW electrical and exporting 33.72MW..." and so for this purpose we assume that plant level losses are already accounted for in the conversion factor.

3.3 Commercial cost

The commercial opportunity cost represents the financial value associated with the electricity which is not generated due to heat extraction. The core principle here is that the plant will, at least, be made whole in consideration of the foregone electricity sale opportunity. In principle this would make the plant agnostic to the choice between exporting electricity only or exporting heat and electricity. The opportunity cost is calculated as the product of the foregone electricity volume, provided by the conversion factor from the generation opportunity cost, multiplied by an indicative electricity price, thereby completing the translation of the physical generation cost into economic terms and deriving a total opportunity cost.

In this calculation, a key parameter is the 'indicative electricity price'. Ultimately it would come down to the plant to assess what they would consider to be a reasonable value for this based on their anticipated gross margin which will vary depending on trading strategies and market participation. In the simplest case, as is often the case in literature, a single reference market price is used, however in practice this approach may not fully capture the complexity of revenue streams available to generation assets. In the GB market, participation in different markets; day-ahead auctions, intraday auctions, continuous intraday trading, Net Imbalance Volume (NIV) chasing, or participation in the Balancing Mechanism, all introduce additional sources of revenue which can materially influence plant margin through additional extrinsic value. To capture this, two representative cases are considered.

The first assumes an unhedged trading strategy in which the EfW plant participates in standard GB electricity markets through a combination of day-ahead and intraday trading. Recognising that electricity market optimisation is not the primary function of an EfW facility, the analysis adopts a simplified trading strategy whereby the majority of generation is committed through day-ahead markets, with the remaining volume exposed to intraday prices. This approach provides a realistic representation of how electricity revenues may be realised while avoiding the additional complexity associated with continuous trading, forecasting uncertainty and market liquidity considerations.

The second case reflects the commercial reality that many EfW operators have access to fixed-price power purchase agreements (PPAs) alongside wholesale market participation. Under this scenario, the plant can choose between fixed-price and market-based routes to market for different proportions of its output. The resulting electricity price index therefore reflects the most commercially advantageous combination of fixed-price and wholesale revenues available to the plant. In effect, the approach assumes that the operator will rationally select the sales strategy that maximises electricity revenues and therefore represents the true opportunity cost of diverting generation towards heat production.

By considering both hedged and unhedged trading arrangements, the analysis captures a realistic range of electricity values that may be available to the EfW facility. These values form the basis of the opportunity-cost calculation and allow the subsequent optimisation model to assess how heat production and thermal storage interact with evolving electricity market conditions.

4 Thermal storage model

While the opportunity-cost framework establishes a transparent basis for valuing heat, it does not in itself resolve the operational challenges associated with integrating EfW-derived heat into a district heating network. The value of heat is inherently influenced by timing. Heat demand fluctuates throughout the day and across seasons, while electricity prices vary according to broader market conditions. Without flexibility, the EfW facility must continuously balance these competing requirements, often resulting in suboptimal outcomes for both heat and electricity production. Thermal energy storage provides a mechanism for overcoming this constraint by decoupling heat generation from heat consumption and creating additional opportunities for system optimisation.

The importance of flexibility within future energy systems has increased significantly in recent years. As electricity systems become increasingly reliant on intermittent renewable generation, wholesale electricity prices have become more volatile. Periods of low demand combined with high renewable output can result in very low electricity prices, while periods of system stress may lead to substantial price spikes. For conventional electricity generators, these fluctuations create both risks and opportunities. For CHP operators, however, the challenge is more complex because heat demand imposes an additional operational constraint.

Without storage, heat must generally be produced when it is required by consumers. This means that CHP operators may be forced to extract heat even during periods when electricity prices are high and electricity generation would otherwise be commercially attractive. Conversely, during periods of low electricity prices, opportunities to recover additional heat may be constrained by a lack of immediate demand. The result is a system that cannot fully exploit either heat or electricity market conditions.

Thermal storage addresses this problem by introducing temporal flexibility. Heat can be captured during periods when electricity market conditions make CHP operation attractive and subsequently stored until it is required by consumers. Equally, stored heat can be discharged during periods when electricity prices incentivise maximising electrical output. In effect, storage allows heat demand and electricity market signals to be considered independently rather than simultaneously.

From a commercial perspective, this flexibility transforms the role of recovered heat within the wider energy system. Rather than being valued solely at the moment of production, heat becomes a resource that can be strategically deployed in response to changing market conditions. This capability is particularly important within the opportunity-cost framework developed in this study because the value of foregone electricity generation varies continuously over time. By allowing heat production to occur when electricity opportunity costs are relatively low, storage can reduce the average cost of heat supplied to the network while maintaining generator revenues.

5 Techno-economic modelling framework

To evaluate the combined effects of opportunity-cost pricing and thermal storage, a techno-economic optimisation model was developed using the Pyomo python modelling framework. The model represents the interaction between three principal system components: the EfW facility, the thermal storage asset and the district heating network.

The optimisation framework seeks to minimise the overall cost of heat supply while ensuring that heat demand is satisfied throughout the study period. At each time step, the model determines whether heat should be supplied directly to consumers, stored for future use, or discharged from storage to meet demand. The optimisation is constrained by plant heat export capacity, storage limitations, transmission losses and heat demand requirements.

A key feature of the model is its incorporation of temporally varying electricity prices. This enables the economic consequences of CHP operation to be evaluated under realistic market conditions. The framework therefore captures the dynamic interaction between electricity market value, heat demand and storage operation, providing a more comprehensive assessment than static cost-based approaches.

The resulting model allows different storage capacities and operational strategies to be compared, providing insight into the circumstances under which thermal storage delivers economic value. Importantly, the framework also enables the calculation of the

levelised cost of heat (LCoH), facilitating direct comparison between alternative system configurations.

6 Discussion

The analysis highlights the importance of commercial design in determining the viability of EfW heat utilisation. While the technical capability to recover and distribute waste heat is well established, investment decisions are often constrained by uncertainty regarding heat value and long-term revenue streams. By linking heat prices directly to observable electricity market outcomes, the opportunity-cost framework developed in this study provides a transparent mechanism for reducing this uncertainty.

The results also demonstrate the strategic value of thermal storage. Beyond its role in improving system resilience, storage acts as a commercial hedge between heat and electricity markets. By enabling heat production to be shifted across time, storage allows low-value heat to be captured and utilised during periods when electricity market conditions would otherwise make heat extraction uneconomic. This flexibility reduces average heat costs while maintaining generator revenues.

Figure 2: Cumulative cost of heat for 5MWh incremental storage capacity

A preliminary run of the model illustrates this by examining cumulative heat costs across the calendar year of 2024 when utilising heat from the EfW mixed with heat storage in increments of 5MWh heat storage capacity. The results, presented in Figure 2, show a significant decrease in heat cost across the year as heat storage capacity increases. This incremental reduction in cost grows increasingly less significant between storage capacities as heat storage tank size increases, suggesting an optimal storage capacity relative to heat demand which can be investigated in more detail.

More broadly, the research demonstrates the benefits of integrated infrastructure planning. The proposed coordination between waste management, district heating and extractive industries creates opportunities that would be difficult to realise through isolated sectoral planning. In particular, the use of quarry infrastructure for thermal storage highlights the potential for innovative co-development approaches to reduce capital costs and accelerate deployment of low-carbon energy systems.

The framework developed here is not specific to East Lothian and could be applied to other regions seeking to utilise EfW heat resources or indeed any other heat producing technologies. As electricity systems continue to decarbonise and market volatility

increases, the ability to optimise interactions between heat and power systems is likely to become increasingly valuable.

7 Conclusions

This paper has presented an integrated framework for utilising waste heat from EfW facilities within district heating networks. Through the combination of opportunity-cost-based heat pricing and large-scale thermal energy storage, the research addresses two of the principal barriers to EfW heat deployment: commercial uncertainty and operational inflexibility.

The opportunity-cost methodology provides a transparent and economically grounded basis for valuing heat by explicitly recognising the revenue sacrificed through reduced electricity generation. Thermal storage complements this framework by introducing flexibility between heat generation and demand, allowing the system to respond more effectively to dynamic electricity market conditions. Using the East Lothian Heat Project as a case study, the research demonstrates how coordinated planning across waste management, heat infrastructure and extractive industries can unlock commercially viable pathways for low-carbon heat deployment. The resulting framework offers a scalable and replicable model for local authorities and developers seeking to accelerate the transition towards affordable, resilient and low-carbon heating systems.

The analysis presented here should be viewed as the first stage of a broader research programme. The modelling framework necessarily relies on a number of simplifying assumptions relating to heat demand profiles, electricity market participation strategies, storage performance, transmission losses and plant operating characteristics. While these assumptions provide an appropriate basis for developing and demonstrating the framework, further work is required to assess the sensitivity of the results to variations in these parameters. Future research will therefore focus on a comprehensive sensitivity analysis to evaluate the robustness of the opportunity-cost valuation methodology and the economic performance of thermal storage under a range of plausible operating conditions and market environments.

Particular attention will be given to the influence of electricity price volatility, alternative hedging strategies, storage sizing decisions, heat demand uncertainty and thermal losses on the levelised cost of heat. This will provide greater insight into the conditions under which thermal storage delivers the greatest economic and social benefit and help identify the key drivers of project viability. In doing so, future work will strengthen the evidence base for investment decisions and support the wider application of the framework to other EfW and district heating developments across the UK.

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